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InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

D6.2 SOIL HEALTH CERTIFICATION IN THE CARBON FARMING FRAMEWORK

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Soil health certification in the carbon farming framework

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1. Executive Summary

Purpose

This deliverable explores how soil health indicators can be integrated into the EU Carbon Farming Certification Framework, complementing carbon-centric metrics with a more holistic approach. The aim is to ensure accountability for multiple soil-related benefits while promoting synergies with other EU policies, including the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive, the Nature Restoration Regulation, and the Common Agricultural Policy.

Intended Audience

The report is primarily intended for EU and national policymakers, certification bodies, and stakeholders involved in carbon farming, soil health monitoring, and climate policy. It is also relevant for researchers and land managers seeking practical approaches to embed soil health into carbon farming schemes.

Description of Main Activities

The work involved:

- Analysing the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation and its certification methodologies.
- Assessing the wider EU policy framework to identify synergies and avoid trade-offs.
- Selecting and testing soil health indicators in InBestSoil case studies across diverse biogeographic regions, focusing on agricultural sites.
- Testing an indicator-based approach for certifying soil health as a voluntary co-benefit within carbon farming schemes, using data from the selected sites.

Key Results

- A multi-indicator framework combining physical, chemical, and biological metrics was proposed to assess soil health co-benefits.
- SOC-based indicator: The Observed/Typical SOC (O/T SOC) index emerged as a practical and less biased alternative to the SOC/clay ratio for evaluating soil structural quality.
- Positive impacts: Carbon farming practices tested in InBestSoil agricultural sites generally improved soil structural quality, nutrient cycling, and microbial biomass compared to conventional management.
- Policy alignment: Strong synergies were identified between carbon farming certification and the Soil Monitoring Directive, Nature Restoration Regulation, and CAP eco-schemes.

Research and Practice Implications

The findings highlight the feasibility of integrating soil health indicators into carbon farming certification, offering a pathway to incentivize multifunctional land management. Future research should refine indicator thresholds and explore cost-effective monitoring solutions, while practice should focus on harmonizing soil health assessments with existing EU frameworks to reduce administrative burden.

Policy Implications

To maximize benefits, EU and national authorities should embed soil health indicators into certification methodologies, align monitoring with the Soil Monitoring Directive, and promote synergies with CAP and restoration targets. Establishing regional benchmarks and supporting capacity building will be key to successful implementation.

Conclusion

By incorporating soil health into carbon farming certification, the EU can accelerate the transition toward sustainable land management, delivering climate, biodiversity, and socio-economic benefits. This approach strengthens the Soil Mission objectives and provides a robust foundation for future policy development.

2. Introduction

The European Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/3012) represents a significant step towards incentivizing practices that contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation through verifiable carbon removal efforts. Among these, carbon farming is particularly relevant for achieving Soil Mission objectives for its dual aim to not only mitigate climate change but also improve soil health. Indeed, the focus of the carbon farming certification framework is on the quantification of carbon removals and soil emission reductions, but carbon farming activities are also required to provide co-benefits in terms of soil health improvement. However, although the broader ecological and agronomic benefits associated with improved soil functions are a key driver for farmers, the carbon farming certification methodologies being currently developed will not include a framework for voluntary co-benefits.

This deliverable (D6.2) addresses this gap by exploring how soil health indicators identified and developed in WP3 “Economic valuation of the soil ecosystem services and the impacts of soil interventions” can complement carbon-centric metrics within the carbon farming certification framework. The aim is to propose a more holistic and robust certification framework that ensures accountability for multiple soil-related benefits, including water regulation, nutrient cycling, and resilience to climate stress, in synergy with other relevant EU policies.

By analysing the methodological and normative underpinnings of the CRCF Regulation, as well as benchmarking against state-of-the-art scientific knowledge, this report outlines a set of indicators and evaluation criteria that can be used to better embed soil health considerations within the carbon farming certification framework and in the broader EU policy context. Insights from other relevant Soil Mission projects (e.g., BENCHMARKS and AI4SoilHealth) as well as EJP Soil are considered, to ensure consistency and optimize efforts. Presenting findings from InBestSoil case studies, this report illustrates how such an indicator-based approach can be practically implemented and generate socio-economic value for land managers.

2.1 InBestSoil case studies

InBestSoil includes nine case studies, i.e., seven Lighthouses (LHs) and two Living Labs (LLs), covering agricultural, forestry, urban, and industrial land uses across four biogeographic regions (Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean) (Figure 1, Table 1). Adopting the definition by the Implementation Plan for the Soil Mission, LHs serve as demonstration of long-term solutions, and are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement. In line with the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), LLs are intended as collaborations among research and innovation ecosystems, which involve regional stakeholders in systemic research and codesign, to jointly improve the effectiveness of new practices on soil health. To compare soil health between two contrasting scenarios (long-term sustainable management vs unsustainable management), each LH is associated with a nearby area with expected low soil health, that is used as a reference. In addition to long-term sites (lighthouses), LLs include experimental sites where different soil management practices are adopted.

Among InBestSoil case studies, LH7, LL1 and LL2 have an agricultural land use and would be eligible for carbon farming certification (section 4.1). In LH7, the two contrasting scenarios are biodynamic (with diverse crop rotations, reduced tillage, legumes and green manures) and conventional (with pesticides, herbicides, conventional tillage and green manures). In LL1, two lighthouse sites (Ussana and Benatzu) and nine experimental sites are used to test the effect of reduced tillage and sod seeding against conventional tillage. In LL2, three long-term sites are used to test different cropping systems, while four treatments are tested within an experimental site: bioorganic, biodynamic, conventional with organic and mineral fertilization, and conventional with only mineral fertilization.

Figure 1: Map with the location of the lighthouses (LH) and living labs (LL) of InBestSoil, with the strategy followed in each of them.

Table 1: Main characteristics of InBestSoil Lighthouses (LH) and Living Labs (LL).

LH/LL	Location	Land use	Challenges addressed	Since	Proposed solutions / Opportunities
LH1	Extremadura, Spain	Livestock farming, Agriculture	Poor land use and loss of fertility	1993	Carbon storage opportunities in forest soils. Increased fertility and soil quality through herbivores "carbon pump" and "rotational grazing"
LH2	Salamanca, Spain	Old Uranium mine	Overexploitation, soil abandonment, loss of structure and polluted flood risk near urban areas.	2006	Restored using artificial soils: technosols
LH3	Galicia, Spain	Old copper mine	Profound degradation of the environment, lack of vegetation and soil cover, rapid	1989	Restored using artificial soils: technosols

			oxidation generating a hyper-acidic mine drainage which contaminates the nearby rivers		
LH4	Zagreb, Croatia	Forest, Apple Orchard, Abandoned agricultural land, Grassland	Overexploitation, soil abandonment, compaction, and flood risk near urban areas	1991	Promoting sustainable natural processes: mulching, low soil disturbance, maintaining vegetation cover
LH5	Vilnius, Lithuania	Urban gardens, recreation	Poor land use, and risk of soil erosion and flooding in urban areas	2001	Flood regulation, Erosion regulation, Food production, Carbon sequestration, Recreation
LH6	Vidzeme, Latvia	Forests, recreation area	Diverse soil organic matter content, Unbalanced soil nutrient content, Soil acidification, Soil erosion on slopes	2001	Forest fertilization experiments, Forest regeneration on slopes and lowland parts, Natural and human promoted afforestation
LH7	Betuwe, Netherlands	Agriculture	Reduced soil fertility, biodiversity and ecosystem services and need to extend crop diversifications	2008	Minimize the time in which the soil is bare; Alternative organic fertilization; developing business cases around N-fixing crops;
LL1	Sardinia, Italy	Agriculture	Reduced soil fertility, biodiversity and ecosystem services associated with conventional agriculture	2003	Conservation agriculture
LL2	Cantons Basel Landschaft and Basel-Stadt, Switzerland	Agriculture	Intensive agriculture depletes SOM and increases the risk of soil erosion, loss of soil biodiversity and overall soil quality.	2021	Improved soil management, farm-specific soil organic matter build-up plan is developed with advisors, C-farming + C-credits

3. Methodology

The main objective of the project InBestSoil is “to co-create a framework for investment in conservation and recovery of soil health, by developing an economic valuation system of the ecosystem services delivered by a healthy soil and the impacts of soil interventions, and its incorporation into business models and incentives”. The specific objective of Task 6.2 “Soil health certification approaches” is to investigate how soil health indicators could be included within carbon farming certification methodologies, in consultation with stakeholders. To do so, a methodological approach composed of several steps was followed.

3.1 Analysis of CRCF Regulation

As soon as it was officially adopted, the CRCF Regulation was analysed in all its aspects, but with a focus on Carbon Farming. Despite not being part of the Expert Groups supporting the development of delegated acts for certification methodologies, the process was followed closely by viewing recordings of expert group meetings (available at this [link](#)), participating to an open workshop on 'Soil carbon in mineral soils and agroforestry' (November 26, 2024) and attending the 2nd EU Carbon Farming Summit (Dublin, 4-6 March 2025).

Common methodologies will focus on the certification of carbon removals, including how to quantify carbon units (one unit= 1 t CO₂eq ha⁻¹) and guidelines for the demonstration of minimum sustainability requirements and mandatory co-benefits, but will not provide rules for the certification of additional voluntary co-benefits. As the latter are linked to the provision of several ecosystem services and are key to giving more economic value to the certified units, they were the focus of Task 6.2.

3.2 Assessment of the wider EU policy framework

As highlighted in Deliverable 6.1 "Policy conditions and catalogues of existing soil health economic and policy incentives", the EU policy framework is transitioning from a fragmented system to a coherent one, revolving around the recently adopted Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive (COM/2023/416 final). The long-term ambition of the Directive is to achieve healthy soils by 2050, with enhanced monitoring, harmonized data, integrated agricultural and climate incentives, and a clearer legal foundation. Further, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP, REGULATION (EU) 2021/2115) is the main EU instrument influencing soil management, while the Nature Restoration Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991) sets binding targets that have direct connections with Carbon Farming mandatory co-benefits. A coherent policy framework is essential to avoid trade-offs and promote synergies between policies, increasing the success of implementation measures. To this end, the three aforementioned policies were analysed to identify key elements of potential synergy.

3.3 Identification of indicators in consultation with stakeholders

According to the BENCHMARKS project, "to guarantee successful measurements of soil health, the harmonization of European soil (health) monitoring is essential, while at the same time indicators should be context-specific to ensure that the results are meaningful and fit for purpose" (Deliverable 4.2. "Comparing national soil sampling procedures with LUCAS and those proposed in BENCHMARKS"). Aligning with this approach, relevant soil health indicators were identified within Task 3.1 in consultation with local stakeholders (Deliverable 3.1. "Toolkit of soil health indicators with metrics"), and were measured in all InBestSoil case studies in 2023. To reflect on the relevance of different carbon farming activities in the local context, case study leaders prioritized different practices during an online

workshop on Jun 18, 2024. Based on the outcomes of the workshop and on CRCF eligibility criteria, the three agricultural case studies (LH7, LL1 and LL2) were identified as suitable for carbon farming certification. Another online workshop with case study leaders was conducted on June 19, 2025 to ensure that the results obtained from the measurement of soil health indicators are meaningful for local stakeholders. The workshop was organized in collaboration with WP2 "Stakeholder communities for co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning" and WP4 "Impacts and scalability of current soil health interventions across Europe", to ensure alignment within different project activities. Prior to the workshop, data for all indicators was analysed with simple statistics by WP3 "Economic valuation of the soil ecosystem services and the impacts of soil interventions" partners to assess differences between treatments and identify indicators that reveal changes (i.e., sensitive) (Annex I). During the workshop, quantitative results were presented to case study leaders using a Miro board to reflect on their meaning and gather insights (Annex II). Further, follow-up meetings with the agricultural sites (LH7, LL1 and LL2) allowed more in-depth discussions and a better understanding of the context. Partners in charge of LL1 and LL2 highlighted which comparisons among trials (lighthouse sites or experimental/on farm trials) are meaningful. In particular, lighthouse sites for LL1 and experimental trials for LL2 (see section 2.1).

Lastly, communication and dissemination through the SoilCommunity Platform, developed within Task 2.3. "Development and maintenance of InBestSoil a digital collaboration platform for LHs and LLs", ensured knowledge exchange with other relevant projects and all interested stakeholders. In particular, two webinars on the Carbon Farming Certification Framework (March 28 and November 27, 2025) were organized by Task 2.3 in collaboration with the project BIOServicES, involving representatives from the projects CREDIBLE, AGROECOseqC and MRV4SOC.

3.4 Soil health certification approach

All the insights gathered in the previous steps were assessed against state-of-the-art scientific knowledge on soil health indicators and payments for ecosystem services (PES), to define a soil health certification approach that could be integrated within carbon farming methodologies. Data from the three InBestSoil agricultural case studies (LH7, LL1 and LL2) were used to assess the effectiveness of the proposed approach in capturing the impact of carbon farming practices on soil health and related ecosystem services.

4. The EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation

The CRCF Regulation was officially adopted on December 6, 2024, establishing the first EU-wide voluntary framework for certifying carbon removals, including carbon farming and carbon storage in products, and reflecting the EU's broader ambition to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. By defining clear quality criteria

and introducing homogenized monitoring and reporting requirements, the framework aims to boost confidence in carbon removal claims and support investment in both technological and nature-based solutions.

The CRCF Regulation sets out common rules for quantifying and validating carbon removal activities, including soil-based approaches like carbon farming. The European Commission defines carbon farming as “climate-friendly practices implemented by farmers and foresters to enhance carbon sequestration and storage in forests and soils, as well as reduce greenhouse gas emissions from soils” (https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/carbon-removals-and-carbon-farming_en). Carbon farming practices include rewetting and restoring peatlands and wetlands, agroforestry, soil protection through cover cropping or conservation tillage, reforestation, and improving fertiliser use efficiency.

According to the CRCF Regulation “The Commission should establish, by means of delegated acts, detailed certification methodologies for the different types of activities provided for in this Regulation, taking into account their specific characteristics in order to enable operators to apply, in a standardised, verifiable, cost-effective and comparable way, the quality criteria laid down in this Regulation”. To advise the Commission on the development of such certification methodologies, an Expert Group on carbon removals was established, including national authorities, businesses, NGOs, and research institutions.

At the time of the development of this Deliverable, the Commission is working on finalizing certification methodologies, with an emphasis on robust monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) procedures, combined with minimum sustainability criteria and mandatory co-benefits to ensure that carbon benefits do not come at the expense of other environmental objectives. Additionality and liability requirements are the other key elements of the certification framework, but they will not be discussed within this report as to keep the focus on soil health-related aspects.

4.1 Carbon farming certification methodologies

To reflect the specific characteristics of different carbon farming practices, methodologies are being developed for three groups of activities:

- Agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils: eligible activities include practices carried out on mineral agricultural soils (cropland and grassland). These include agricultural practices that increase carbon removals in soils or reduce emissions of carbon from soils, agroforestry practices, and practices that reduce direct and indirect nitrous oxide emissions from managed agricultural soils.
- Planting of trees: eligible activities are those resulting in the planting of trees on grassland, cropland, settlements and degraded forest land. Trees should have covered a maximum of 10% of the activity area in the 20 years prior the carbon farming activity.
- Peatland rewetting and restoration: eligible activities include removing aboveground structures causing the drainage or modification of natural water flows and altering the pumping regime to decrease water table

fluctuations. The activities shall result in the rewetting of organic soils, including those used for agriculture and forestry, and in a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

Among InBestSoil case studies, LH7, LL1 and LL2 would be eligible for "Agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils", while other case studies do not fully match the other two categories. Thus, the following sections focus on the first group of activities.

4.1.1 Net Carbon benefits

The methodology for quantifying carbon removals for carbon farming activities focus on two key elements: the *Temporary net carbon removal benefit* and the *Net soil emission reduction benefit*. Based on the information derived from the last Expert Group meeting (May 8, 2025), the most recent draft of the methodology¹ for agricultural mineral soil foresees the quantification of net benefits as:

Temporary net carbon removal benefit =

$$(CR_{\text{baseline}} - CR_{\text{activity}} - GHG_{\text{associated}}) \times (1 - UNC)$$

Net soil emission reduction benefit =

$$(LSE_{\text{baseline}} - LSE_{\text{activity}} + ASE_{\text{activity}} - GHG_{\text{associated}}) \times (1 - UNC)$$

Where:

CR = Carbon Removals (Soil organic carbon and woody biomass)

LSE = LULUCF² Soil Emissions (Soil organic carbon)

ASE = Agricultural Soil Emissions (Non-CO₂ agricultural emissions)

GHG_{associated} = Associated Greenhouse Gas emissions (e.g., off-farm emissions)

UNC = Uncertainty

Carbon stock changes (CR, LSE) must be quantified for each part of land or parcel where the carbon farming activity is implemented. Agricultural Soil emission reductions (ASE) must be quantified for the entire area under the farmer's operational control. Different approaches to establishing the baseline have been proposed, including the identification of an activity-specific baseline as well as using a zero baseline. Since different approaches can lead to significantly different results, this has been one of the most critical points in the development of certification methodologies.

¹ **Source:** <https://webcast.ec.europa.eu/expert-group-meeting-cf-methodology-1draft-methodology-on-agroforestry-on-mineral-soils-2025-05-08>

² **LULUCF** = Land Use, Land Use Change, and Forestry. In the context of national greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 2019), LULUCF is a GHG inventory sector that covers anthropogenic emissions and removals of GHG in managed lands, excluding non-CO₂ agricultural emissions, which are included under ASE.

Further, it should be possible to use different methods for the quantification of different components:

	Use of Tier 3 model	Measure-remeasure	Remote sensing	Tier 1 or 2 emission factors
Soil organic carbon	YES	YES	Only for data input	NO
Woody biomass	(YES)	YES	YES	NO
Soil N₂O emissions	YES	NO	NO	YES
GHG_{associated}	(YES)	NO	NO	YES

4.1.2 Minimum sustainability requirements

Minimum sustainability requirements ensure that carbon farming activities comply with existing environmental legislation across several areas:

- Climate Change Mitigation: Covered by the activity's eligibility requirements (e.g., reducing emissions or increasing removals).
- Climate Change Adaptation: Requires carrying out an ex-ante risk assessment and mitigating risks if necessary, including the use of climate-proof tree species.
- Sustainable Use and Protection of Water and Marine Sources: Compliance with the Water Framework Directive, securing a permit for water abstraction, and maintenance of riparian buffer zones are required.
- Transition to a Circular Economy: Requires compliance with national rules for the collection, recycling, and disposal of waste materials.
- Pollution Prevention and Control: Compliance with national action programs under the Nitrates Directive and the Directive on sustainable use of pesticides, including adherence to principles of integrated pest management.
- Protection and Restoration of Biodiversity and Ecosystems (including soil health):
 - No negative effects in relation to Natura 2000 sites.
 - Compliance with national requirements from the Nature Restoration Regulation outside Natura 2000 areas.
 - No detrimental effects on the recovery or maintenance of populations under the Habitats and Birds Directives.
 - No disturbance of legally protected species.
 - Protection of existing buffer zones and ecological corridors.
 - Prevention of the introduction of invasive alien species.

4.1.3 Co-benefits

According to the CRCF Regulation, carbon farming activities are required to generate mandatory co-benefits for the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health and the avoidance of land degradation. Additionally, "Operators or groups of operators should be able to report co-benefits that contribute to the sustainability objectives beyond the minimum sustainability requirements. To that end, their reporting should comply with the certification methodologies tailored to the different carbon removal activities developed by the Commission. Certification methodologies should, as much as possible, incentivise the generation of co-benefits for biodiversity going beyond the minimum sustainability requirements, with a view to generating a market premium for the certified units, by including, for instance, positive lists of activities that are deemed to generate co-benefits".

While Net carbon benefits will be assessed with a result-based approach (i.e., payments are made based on the quantified effect in terms of net carbon removals and soil emission reductions), mandatory co-benefits will be certified with an action-based approach (i.e., demonstrating the implementation of specific practices). In particular, carbon farming activities must demonstrate one or more of the following to comply with mandatory requirements:

- Beneficial impact demonstrated in peer-reviewed scientific literature.
- Includes at least one of the measures listed in the typology of measures which will be developed by the Commission, in alignment with the Nature Restoration Regulation.
- Qualitatively demonstrated to be effective at improving or maintaining the good condition of habitats in line with the Habitats and Birds Directives or as indicated in the EU wide mapping of ecosystem conditions.
- For agroforestry practices, the activity aligns with the recommendations from the EU guidelines for biodiversity-friendly afforestation, reforestation, and tree planting.

Since mandatory co-benefits will not generate a market premium for the certified units, an action-based approach was promoted to avoid an additional unremunerated burden for operators. On the other hand, operators that choose to verify the generation of additional voluntary co-benefits would be able to obtain a market premium for the certified units. The monetary value of such premium would be best determined through a result-based approach that links payment to positive outcomes in terms of ecosystem services (Burton & Schwarz, 2013). However, since most ecosystem services are difficult to measure, PES schemes are often based on proxy actions or indicators.

Based on the information derived from the last Expert Group meeting, no clear indication on how to demonstrate and monitor voluntary co-benefits will be provided, and operators will have the freedom to choose their methodology. The lessons learned during the pilot phase of the certification framework will be used for the update of methodologies.

5. The EU policy framework

5.1 Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive

On October 23, 2025, the European Parliament officially adopted the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive. This legislation establishes the first-ever EU framework for assessing and monitoring soils, setting the ambitious goal of ensuring healthy soils across Europe by 2050. Under the directive, member states must establish monitoring systems to assess soil physical, chemical, and biological conditions, following a common EU methodology. Further, member states shall determine soil districts and soil units that cover their entire territory. Soil districts shall serve administrative purposes, while soil units should be defined based on factors such as soil type and land use, with the purpose of ensuring statistical uniformity for monitoring. Within soil units, soil health will be assessed regularly (every 6 years) using common soil descriptors (Table 2) characterized by:

- Non-binding sustainable target values (EU-level values where applicable)
- Operational trigger values (thresholds at which intervention / support is needed, defined at national level)

According to the Directive, “non-binding sustainable target values should reflect, based on the current scientific knowledge, the ideal situation whereby the capacity of soils to provide ecosystem services will not decrease and no significant harm will be caused to human health or the environment.” Further, “the soil monitoring framework shall build on existing monitoring frameworks at national level and Union level including, where appropriate, data from the land use/cover area frame statistical survey (LUCAS)”. Soil health will be monitored within soil units,

The Commission will develop implementing and delegated acts to specify formats and methods for monitoring and reporting soil health information. Once the Directive is adopted by the European Parliament and in force, member states will have three years to transpose the rules into national legislation.

Table 2: Soil descriptors, criteria for healthy soil condition, soil sealing and soil removal indicators foreseen by the Soil Monitoring Directive (source: COM/2023/416 final, Annex I).

Aspect of soil degradation	Soil descriptor	Criteria for healthy soil condition (non-binding sustainable target values)	Land areas exempted from meeting the related criterion
<i>Part A: soil descriptors with criteria for healthy soil condition established at Union level</i>			
Salinisation	Electrical conductivity (deci-Siemens per meter)	< 4 dS m ⁻¹ when using saturated soil paste extract (eEC) measurement method, or equivalent criterion if using another measurement method	Naturally saline land areas, areas with regular flooding from marine submersion and areas subject to sea spray
Loss of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC)	Soil organic Carbon (SOC) concentration (g per kg)	– For organic soils: respect targets set for such soils at national level in accordance with Article 4(2) and (4), and Article 11(4) of Regulation (EU)	No exemption

		2024/1991 (Nature Restoration Law)	
		- For mineral soils: SOC/Clay ratio > 1/13 (that is the ratio of SOC content to the content of the clay fraction (fraction with a diameter of less than 0,002 mm))	Non-managed soils in natural land areas
	Member States are expected to apply corrective factors to the ratio where specific soil types or climatic conditions justify it, taking into account the link to structural stability		
Subsoil compaction	Bulk density in subsoil (g per cm ³)	Soil texture	Non-managed soils in natural land areas and areas with naturally compacted soils
		Sand, loamy sand, sandy loam, loam: <1.80	
		Sandy clay loam, loam, clay loam, silt, silt loam: <1.75	
		Silt loam, silty clay loam: <1,65	
		Sandy clay, silty clay, clay loam with 35-45 % clay: <1.58	
		Clay: <1.47	
	Member States may apply different texture classes or values corresponding to the levels considered problematic for plant rooting system development		
Optional: - saturated hydraulic conductivity – Ksat (cm per day) - air capacity (%)	≥ 10 cm/day ≥ 5 %		
Member States may adapt these values according to their local soil conditions			
<i>Part B: soil descriptors with criteria for healthy soil condition established at Member State level</i>			
Excess nutrient content in soil	Extractable phosphorus (mg per kg)	< 'maximum value' Member States shall lay down their own maximum value, at a level that would not entail damage to human health and the environment	Non-managed soils in natural land areas
Soil erosion	Soil erosion rate (tonnes per hectare per year)	< 'maximum value' Member States shall lay down their own maximum value, at a level that would not entail damage to human health and the environment.	Badlands and natural land areas, except if they represent a significant disaster risk
Soil contamination	- concentration of heavy metals in soil: As, Sb, Cd, Co, Cr (total), Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, Tl, V, Zn (mg per kg) - concentration of a selection of organic contaminants established by	Reasonable assurance, obtained from soil point sampling, identification and investigation of potentially contaminated sites and any other relevant information, that an unacceptable risk to human health and the environment from soil	No exemption

	Member States and taking into account existing concentration limits in Union law, e.g. for water quality and air emissions	contamination does not exist. Natural and anthropogenic background levels shall be taken into account in the risk assessment. If natural background is the only reason leading to unacceptable risks, then the relevant soil shall be deemed to meet the healthy soil criteria provided that it is managed in such a way that an unacceptable risk to human health does not exist. Habitats with a naturally high concentration of heavy metals that are included in Annex I to Directive 92/43/EEC shall remain protected.	
Reduction of soil water retention and infiltration	Water retention: – soil water holding capacity of the soil sample (% of water per total soil (volume or mass)) Water infiltration: – saturated hydraulic conductivity – Ksat (cm per day) – air capacity (%)	The estimated value for the total water holding capacity, the saturated hydraulic conductivity and the air capacity of a soil unit is above the minimal threshold and may also be assessed by river basin or sub-basin, taking into account water processes occurring at that scale The minimal threshold shall be set (in tonnes) by the Member State at the relevant scale, at such a value that the impacts of flooding following intense rain events or of periods of low soil moisture due to drought events are mitigated	No exemption
Loss of SOC	SOC stocks (tC ha ⁻¹) Optional: – soil organic carbon content (g per kg)	Contribute to national targets for net greenhouse gas removals in the LULUCF sector as referred to in Article 4(3) of Regulation (EU) 2018/841 > 'minimum value' Member States shall lay down the minimum value by soil texture	No exemption
<i>Part C: soil descriptors without criteria</i>			
Excess nutrient content in soil	Total nitrogen content in soil (mg g ⁻¹) SOC to nitrogen (C:N) ratio		
Acidification	Soil acidity (pH) Member States may also select the optional descriptor: – base saturation (i.e. (Ca + Mg + K)/effective cation exchange capacity (CEC))		

Topsoil compaction	Bulk density in topsoil (A-horizon) (g cm ⁻³) Optional: – saturated hydraulic conductivity (cm per day) – air capacity (%)
Loss of soil biodiversity	DNA metabarcoding for fungi and bacteria Member States may also select at least one optional soil descriptor for biodiversity, such as: – metabarcoding of archaea, protists and animals – phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PLFA) – abundance and diversity of nematodes – abundance and diversity of earthworms – abundance and diversity of springtails – abundance and diversity of native ants – soil biological quality based on arthropods (QBS-ar) – presence of invasive alien species and plant pests – soil basal respiration
Soil contamination	Concentrations of PFAS-21 or concentrations of PFAS-43 or selected PFAS set by Member States in accordance with Article 7(4) Concentrations of selected active substances in pesticides and their metabolites set by Member States in accordance with Article 7(4) Optional: – concentrations or presence of a selection of other emerging soil contaminants set by Member States in accordance with Article 7(4)
<i>Part D: soil sealing and soil removal indicators</i>	
Soil sealing and soil removal	Total sealed soils and areas that underwent soil removal (km ² and % of Member State surface) Soil sealing and soil removal, de-sealing and net-sealing (average per year – in km ² and % of Member State surface) Total settlement area (km ² and % of Member State surface) Land use change to and from settlement area (average per year – in km ² and % of Member State surface) Member States may also measure other related optional indicators, such as: – soil artificialisation – land fragmentation – land recycling rate – land taken for commercial activities, logistic hubs, renewable energies, surfaces such as airports, roads, mines, – consequences of soil sealing and soil removal, such as quantification of loss of ecosystem services, change in the intensity of floods

Importantly, the soil descriptors foreseen by the Soil Monitoring Directive are linked to different aspects of soil degradation, and the criteria for healthy soil are non-binding target values that serve as a guide to plan interventions. A key element of synergy with the carbon farming certification framework is that data

generated through the regular monitoring of soil descriptors will provide baseline information for assessing the impact of carbon farming activities on soil health.

5.2 Nature Restoration Regulation

The Nature Restoration Regulation aims at restoring at least 20% of the EU's land and sea by 2030, and all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050. It establishes binding restoration targets for degraded ecosystems, with soil-related targets for peatlands and agricultural ecosystems. In particular, member states shall restore 50% of organic soils under agricultural management by 2050, of which at least a third shall be rewet. Agricultural mineral soils shall be monitored for at least two out of the three indicators: grassland butterfly index, soil organic carbon stock, and share of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features. The aim is to achieve increasing trends at national level, and the chosen indicators shall be measured in the period from 18 August 2024 until 31 December 2030, and every six years thereafter. A key element of synergy with the carbon farming certification framework is that mandatory co-benefits for the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health and the avoidance of land degradation, could be certified in alignment with requirements from the Nature Restoration Regulation.

5.3 Common Agricultural Policy

The CAP addresses soil health through a mix of mandatory baseline rules, voluntary payments to reward better practices, financial and advisory support. In particular, conditionality establishes mandatory requirements to maintain Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs), e.g., maintaining permanent grassland, and setting minimum soil cover and nutrient application limits. Beyond these mandatory rules, the CAP offers eco-schemes under Pillar I that reward farmers for voluntary soil-friendly actions like cover cropping, reduced tillage, and diversified rotations. Under Pillar II, agri-environment-climate measures (AECMs) and organic-farming support provide longer-term commitments to improve soil health. Complementary investment aid and advisory services further help farmers adopt precision technologies and sustainable practices. Which exact measures farmers can use depends on each Member State's CAP Strategic Plan, but the most common are: cover crops, reduced tillage, diversified crop rotations including legumes, buffer strips, peatland rewetting, protection of organic soils, precision fertilization, agroforestry and other perennial features. As such, the CAP supports practices that are very well aligned with activities promoted by the CRCF Regulation. Delegated acts will clarify how to ensure that the additionality test is complied with (i.e., citing from the CRCF Regulation: "the incentive effect of the certification under this Regulation is needed for the activity to become financially viable").

6. Certification of soil health as a carbon farming co-benefit

One of the key insights from the 2nd EU Carbon Farming Summit is that “Carbon farming must go beyond carbon”. As emerged from farmers and land managers participating at the Summit, carbon itself is not something that is easily valued and understood, and “rather, carbon farming should be seen as a mechanism to provide incentives for land managers to kick start in Europe a transition towards farming systems that better support a variety of ecosystem services”³. In this sense, integrating the certification of soil health benefits into the carbon farming framework would provide a more relatable outcome, while increasing the monetary value of the certified units if the benefits go beyond mandatory requirements. Key aspects of soil health that can be evaluated in connection with carbon farming activities include soil structure, fertility, biological activity, nutrient cycling, and water regulation. All these properties are largely influenced by soil organic carbon (SOC) in interaction with soil texture, land use, and climate. Measuring these attributes would allow an assessment of how management practices contribute to maintaining or enhancing soil health over time, thus its ability to provide multiple ecosystem services.

To ensure that soil health co-benefits are credibly accounted for, different methodological approaches can be integrated into carbon farming schemes. To be accepted and generate value for the operators, the certification of voluntary co-benefits should not be an extra burden for them, but at the same time it should be scientifically sound and reliable. In the PES realm, action- or result-based schemes can be adopted. The first ones reward land managers for adopting predefined management practices that are expected to reduce environmental impacts. Result-based schemes, by contrast, link payments to demonstrated ecological improvements, assessed through the measured change in indicators. Although action-based schemes have been the most common approach up to now, paying for the provision of actual benefits is often seen as more efficient because it ensures that the desired outcomes are achieved while allowing farmers flexibility in how to do it (Burton & Schwarz, 2013). Yet this approach places greater risk on land managers, since the results depend partly on factors beyond their control, while involving higher monitoring costs (Herzon et al., 2018). To address this, PES schemes may need to compensate for added risk, or may combine a guaranteed participation payment with a bonus for achieving the desired results.

As presented in section 4.1, the CRCF Regulation foresees the certification of Net carbon benefits and soil emissions reductions with a result-based approach, while an action-based approach will be adopted for minimum sustainability requirements and mandatory co-benefits, which don't generate a market premium. The provision of co-benefits beyond mandatory requirements can be rewarded with a premium on the certified units, as long as appropriate methodologies for the certification of such benefits are adopted, i.e., measuring relevant indicators.

³ Sources: <https://www.climate-kic.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/CF-Summit-Webinar-PPT-Slides.pdf> and <https://www.project-credible.eu/news/it's-not-only-about-carbon-the-importance-of-a-holistic-approach-and-co-benefits>

6.1 What are good indicators of soil health?

While several soil health indicators exist, some may be too difficult or costly to measure, or not be intuitive for non-technical users. Overall, good indicators should be based on agreed scientific methodology and be able to detect changes in a timely manner, allowing remedial or adaptive actions when needed. Further, if indicators should be used to incentivize soil health improving practices, they need to be intuitive, i.e., provide information clearly without ambiguity, be easily understood by policymakers and other non-technical end-users (Layke et al., 2012). Further, as highlighted by the Soil Mission project AI4SoilHealth “balancing the cost of monitoring with the benefit of improved decision-making and outcomes is critical. This may mean choosing between direct and indirect methods of soil health assessment” (Campbell et al., 2024).

Within InBestSoil, a participatory approach was applied to select soil health indicators (Deliverable 3.1: Toolkit of Soil Health Indicators with Metrics), tailored to the specific conditions of LHs and LLs. In each LH and LL the relevant indicators have been measured in 2023, enabling the economic valuation of soil-related ecosystem services (Deliverable 3.2: “Report on economic valuation of ecosystem services and disservices in LHs”) and supporting the co-development of business models that encourage public and private investment in soil health (WP5 “New business models for soil health”). The data collected from LHs and LLs was analysed to identify indicators that are able to discriminate between different management practices (sustainable vs unsustainable reference) (Annex I). On June 19, 2025, a workshop with case study leaders was conducted to discuss the observed data, with the aim to gain contextual insights and identify indicators that are not only sensitive, but also relevant and understandable to stakeholders. Each case study focused on a set of indicators representing provisioning, regulating and supporting ecosystem services. Several case studies reported that most of the results were not as expected (Annex II). Importantly, it emerged that satellite-based indicators (e.g., vegetation cover) did not capture temporal variations in agricultural sites, as they were based only on one observation corresponding to the time of soil sampling during Autumn 2023.

6.2 An indicator-based approach for soil health certification

6.2.1 Alignment with Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive

The integration of soil health indicators into carbon farming certification methodologies, particularly for the certification of voluntary co-benefits, should be designed to leverage and promote synergies with existing EU policies, most notably the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive. This would ensure consistency, reduce duplication, and maximize benefits for soil health, climate, and biodiversity. Further, aligning with soil descriptors and indicators foreseen by the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive would allow having baselines of soil health conditions in soil units (i.e., “a spatially discrete area resulting from the intersection of sets of spatial data used as factors for statistical homogeneity”, established by

each member state). This would facilitate assessing the impact of carbon farming activities on soil health.

Several of the soil descriptors and indicators from the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive are included in the InBestSoil toolkit (Deliverable 3.1: "Toolkit of Soil Health Indicators with Metrics") and have been identified as sensitive to discriminate between managements in the different case studies (Table 3, Annex I). The comparison between reference methodologies ensures that the approaches are equivalent. In some cases, different approaches are adopted, as in the case of soil water retention, with *Water content at field capacity* being measured in InBestSoil instead of *Soil water holding capacity*.

Table 3: Alignment between soil descriptors and indicators from the Soil Monitoring Directive and InBestSoil.

Soil descriptor/indicator	Methodology in Soil Monitoring Directive	InBestSoil method aligned?
SOC concentration (g per kg) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SOC/clay ratio for mineral soils 	ISO 10694 Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion, ensuring all carbon is incinerated. SOC shall be calculated by determining the total carbon content and subtracting the carbon present as carbonate, which shall be determined in accordance with ISO 10693	No (inorganic C is determined in a different way)
Extractable phosphorus (mg per kg)	Preferred: ISO 11263 for spectrometric determination of phosphorus soluble in sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (P-Olsen). Other methods may be used as an alternative	Yes
Concentration of heavy metals in soil: As, Sb, Cd, Co, Cr (total), Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, Tl, V, Zn (mg per kg)	ISO 54321: Aqua Regia	Yes
Water retention: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> soil water holding capacity of the soil sample (% of water per total soil (volume or mass)) Water infiltration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> saturated hydraulic conductivity – Ksat (cm per day) air capacity (%) 	(1) Soil water holding capacity and air capacity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Option 1: LABORATORY: ISO 11274 for determination of the water-retention characteristic Option 2: ESTIMATION: apply pedotransfer functions requiring input variables such as particle size distribution, bulk density, soil organic carbon concentration (2) Saturated hydraulic conductivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Option 1: LABORATORY: ISO 17313: Determination of hydraulic conductivity of saturated porous materials Option 2: ESTIMATION: apply pedotransfer functions requiring input variables such as particle size distribution, bulk density, soil organic carbon concentration 	No

SOC stocks (tC ha ⁻¹) Optional: – soil organic carbon content (g per kg)	Methodology as set out in Annex V to Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 in accordance with the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories	Yes
Total nitrogen content in soil (mg g ⁻¹) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• SOC to nitrogen ratio	Option 1: ISO 11261 for determination of total soil nitrogen using a modified Kjeldahl method Option 2: ISO 13878 for determination of total nitrogen by dry combustion	Yes (option 2)
Soil acidity (pH) Member States may also select the optional descriptor: – base saturation (i.e. (Ca + Mg + K)/effective cation exchange capacity (CEC))	ISO 10390 for determination of pH in H ₂ O, KCl and CaCl ₂ extract ISO 11260 for determination of effective cation exchange capacity and base saturation level using BaCl ₂	Yes
Bulk density in topsoil (A-horizon ⁷) (g cm ⁻³)	ISO 11272 for determination of dry bulk density	Yes
DNA metabarcoding for fungi and bacteria Additionally: – metabarcoding of archaea, protists and animals – phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PLFA) – abundance and diversity of nematodes – abundance and diversity of earthworms – abundance and diversity of springtails – abundance and diversity of native ants – soil biological quality based on arthropods (QBS-ar) – presence of invasive alien species and plant pests – soil basal respiration	Use European or international standards where available; if such standard is not available, the methodology chosen shall either be available in the scientific literature or publicly available	Yes

While the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive links soil descriptors to aspects of soil degradation, InBestSoil makes a connection between soil health indicators and ecosystem services. These include provisioning, regulating and supporting services, that can be linked to several key sustainability objectives of the CRCF Regulation (see section 4.1.3). In particular, InBestSoil indicators that are aligned with the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive are related to climate regulation, water purification and soil contaminant reduction, nutrient cycling, flood regulation and water storage, and biodiversity (Annex I).

6.2.2 Soil Organic Carbon based indicators of soil health

Soil organic carbon is a key indicator of soil health due to its influence on physical, chemical, and biological soil properties, and assessing soil health against SOC would require only a minor additional effort to operators who enter the Carbon Farming Certification path. However, assessing SOC levels across diverse soils is challenging because SOC is highly site-specific, influenced by factors such as soil texture and climate. In response to this issue, the SOC/clay ratio has been used to normalize SOC levels and assess soil structural conditions, with predefined thresholds categorizing soils from "degraded" to "very good" (Johannes et al., 2017). In particular, soils with a SOC/clay ratio of at least 1:8 are considered to be in very good condition, between 1:8 and 1:10 good, between 1:10 and 1:13 moderate, and below 1:13 degraded. This indicator has been included in the Soil Monitoring Directive, which sets a threshold of 1:13 as a non-binding sustainable target value (Table 2), and would represent a practical choice for the assessment of soil health co-benefits within the Carbon Farming Certification Framework. However, as demonstrated by Poeplau and Don (2023) using data from 2,958 topsoil samples (0–30 cm depth) from the German Agricultural Soil Inventory, the SOC/clay ratio is biased by clay content, leading to misleading classifications. In their study, clay-rich soils were often classified as "degraded," while sandy soils with low SOC were labeled "very good". This strong clay dependency renders the ratio insensitive to realistic SOC changes due to management or land use.

Using data from the three agricultural sites in InBestSoil (LH7, LL1 and LL2), we verified the relationship between the SOC/clay ratio and the soil clay content, confirming that only soils with less than 11% clay were classified as "very good" (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Relationship between the SOC/clay ratio and the soil clay content in InBestSoil agricultural sites, organized by SOC/clay categories. The number of observations (n) is indicated in the figure for each category.

Based on the notion that in various environmental settings clay content may not be driving SOC accumulation, but rather other soil variables that are important for sorption and stabilization of organic matter, Wenzel et al. (2024) investigated the mechanistic validity and regional applicability of the SOC/clay ratio using extensive data from the Lower Austrian soil database. Indeed, SOC levels were

found to be primarily influenced by amorphous aluminium oxyhydroxides and calcium carbonate equivalents, with minor contributions from clay content and mean annual precipitation. Further, the SOC/clay ratio varied significantly across regions, largely due to differences in parent material and climate, which independently affect clay content and SOC.

To address the limitations of the SOC/clay ratio, Poeplau and Don (2023) proposed a new metric: the ratio of actual SOC to expected SOC, where expected SOC is derived from a regression model based on clay content. This approach provides a less biased normalization and better reflects SOC status relative to regional expectations. Building on this, Feeney et al. (2024) used data from the LUCAS soil monitoring program (19,855 mineral topsoil samples across Europe), to develop a new indicator: Observed SOC/Typical SOC (O/T SOC), where "typical" SOC is the average for a given pedo-climatic zone. Pedo-climatic zones were defined based on land cover, climate (biogeographical region, EEA (2024)), and soil texture (HYPRES, Wösten (2000)). Four index classes were defined based on 25th, 50th and 75th percentiles of O/T SOC for each pedo-climatic zone: "Low" < 25th percentile; "Intermediate" > 25th and < 50th percentiles; "High" > 50th and < 75th percentiles; "Very high" > 75th percentile (Table 4).

Table 4: Predicted typical (mean) Soil Organic Carbon content in each combination of biogeographical region and soil texture class, and the observed/typical SOC index category thresholds (adapted from Feeney et al., 2024).

Biogeographical region	Soil texture class (HYPRES scheme)	Typical SOC g kg⁻¹	Low/intermediate threshold	Intermediate/high threshold	High/very high threshold
Mediterranean	Coarse	5.99	0.68	0.96	1.53
Mediterranean	Fine; Medium; Medium fine; Very fine	12.18	0.71	0.99	1.38
Atlantic	Coarse	19.11	0.7	0.97	1.41
Atlantic and continental	Fine; Medium; Medium fine; Very fine	16.61	0.75	0.96	1.26

The three agricultural sites LH7, LL1 and LL2 are characterized by different climatic conditions and soil texture (Table 5), representing different pedo-climatic zones. By comparing the mean observed SOC in these sites against the typical SOC defined by Feeney et al. (2024), we calculated the O/T SOC index and determined the corresponding category based on the specific threshold values. Across the three case study areas, the majority of observations fell into the high and medium categories (Table 6), showing a less biased relation with soil clay content (Fig. 3) compared to the SOC/clay ratio (Fig. 2).

Table 5: Observed (mean) Soil Organic Carbon content in each combination of biogeographical region and soil texture class for InBestSoil LH7, LL1 and LL2 sites.

LH/LL	Biogeographical region	Soil texture class (HYPRES scheme)	Observed SOC* g kg ⁻¹
LH7	Atlantic	Coarse (n=1)	11.70
		Medium (n=4)	13.98
		Medium fine (n=11)	18.85
LL1	Mediterranean	Coarse (n=7)	8.99
		Medium (n=11)	10.87
LL2	Continental	Medium (n=1)	13.80
		Medium fine (n=15)	14.02

* Mean values across different management types

Table 6: Count of observations for each O/T SOC category across the three InBestSoil agricultural sites.

O/T SOC Category	Count
Very high	3
High	19
Intermediate	20
Low	8

Figure 3: Relationship between the O/T SOC ratio and the soil clay content in InBestSoil agricultural sites, organized by O/T SOC categories.

Soil structure is closely related to SOC. The O/T SOC index was sensitive to differences in porosity (i.e., the portion of soil volume not occupied by solid particles, either mineral or organic, expressed as %) (Fig. 4) and soil bulk density (i.e., soil mass per unit of volume, expressed as g cm⁻³) (Fig. 5) across LH7, LL1 and LL2. As such, the O/T SOC index can provide a good indication of soil structural quality, which is related to soil compaction as well as flood regulation and water storage services.

Figure 4: Relationship between the O/T SOC ratio and soil porosity (%) in InBestSoil agricultural sites, organized by O/T SOC categories.

Figure 5: Relationship between the O/T SOC ratio and the topsoil bulk density (g cm^{-3}) in InBestSoil agricultural sites, organized by O/T SOC categories.

Using data from long-term experiments, Feeney et al. (2024) showed that the O/T SOC index is able to detect changes in time in response to different agricultural management, which is a key requirement for assessing the impact of carbon farming activities on soil health. Nonetheless, several limitations should be noted. First, the reliability of the O/T SOC indicator depends on the dataset used to determine the "typical" SOC; in this case, data from the LUCAS survey from mineral (<20 % organic matter) topsoils (0–20 cm) sampled during 2009–2018. Thus, its applicability to organic soils is uncertain, as well as to different soil depths. Furthermore, SOC is not a universal indicator of soil health. Soils with high O/T SOC can still present excess nutrients or heavy metal contamination. Thus, O/T SOC should be integrated into a multi-indicator framework combining physical, chemical, and biological metrics. In the following section, we test this approach using data from InBestSoil agricultural sites.

7. Soil health assessment in InBestSoil agricultural sites

Data from the three InBestSoil agricultural case studies (LH7, LL1 and LL2) were used to assess the impact of carbon farming practices on soil health and the related ecosystem services. As reported in section 2, two contrasting scenarios were considered in LH7: biodynamic regenerative (with wide crop rotations, reduced tillage, legumes and green manures) and conventional (with pesticides, herbicides, conventional tillage and green manures). In LL1, the two lighthouse sites (Ussana and Benatzu) were used to test the effect of reduced tillage and sod seeding against conventional tillage. In LL2, four systems differing in fertilisation and pest control were considered: biodynamic without chemical pest and weed control and composted manure as organic fertiliser, bioorganic without chemical pest and weed control and manure as organic fertiliser, conventional with chemical pest and weed control and manure as organic fertiliser and mineral fertilization, and conventional with chemical pest and weed control and only mineral fertilization. As such, LH7 and LL2 included management systems that differed in several aspects, while LL1 focused only on the effect of different tillage intensities.

Since provisioning services (e.g., crop yield) have a market value of their own, the focus was on regulating and supporting services. Following the outcomes from the previous steps of Task 6.2, presented in sections 4 to 6, the assessment was based on indicators that ensure alignment with the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive, are meaningful for land managers and don't increase monitoring costs to an extent that is not viable. For each indicator, data are presented using box plots and were analysed with simple statistics (ANOVA test) to compare treatments within each site.

7.1 Soil structural quality for flood regulation and water storage

The O/T SOC indicator was selected as a proxy of soil structural quality, which is linked with the ecosystem service flood regulation and water storage (Fig. 6). In LH7 and LL2, the O/T SOC index was higher in the biodynamic regenerative management compared to the control, while no statistically significant difference was observed in LL1 Ussana (U) and Benatzu (B).

Based on mean O/T SOC values and the reference intervals defined by Feeney et al. (2024) (Table 4), each treatment was assigned to a quality category showing a more nuanced assessment (Table 7). Indeed, except for LL1 B, carbon farming treatments were categorized "higher" compared to conventional controls.

Figure 6: O/T SOC as affected by different management strategies and practices in InBestSoil agricultural sites (LH7: Atlantic, LL1: Mediterranean, LL2: Continental).

Table 7: Mean O/T SOC values in InBestSoil agricultural sites for different management strategies and practices, and corresponding category classes (LH7: Atlantic, LL1: Mediterranean, LL2: Continental).

Site	Management	n	O/T SOC	Category
LH7	Biodyn+reg	8	1.23	Very high
	Conv	8	0.83	Intermediate
LL1_B	Conv till	3	1.00	High
	Red till	3	1.49	High
	Sod seeding	3	0.99	High
LL1_U	Conv till	3	0.75	Intermediate
	Red till	3	1.32	High
	Sod seeding	3	1.21	High
LL2	Biodyn	4	0.99	High
	Biorg	4	0.88	Intermediate

	Conv	4	0.74	Low
	Conv org+min fert	4	0.76	Intermediate

7.2 Soil nitrogen, phosphorous and cation exchange capacity for nutrient cycling

Nutrient cycling was assessed based on total nitrogen (N), extractable phosphorus (P) and cation exchange capacity (CEC). In LL1 total N did not vary among treatments, while in LH7 and LL2 it was significantly higher in biodynamic treatments compared to conventional. Conversely, extractable P was greater in conventional treatments in LL2, while it did not vary significantly in the other sites.

Figure 7: Total N as affected by different management strategies and practices in InBestSoil agricultural sites (LH7: Atlantic, LL1: Mediterranean, LL2: Continental).

Nitrogen and P are the main macronutrients needed for plant growth and, as such, their availability is an indicator of soil fertility. On the other hand, soil N and P are identified as indicators of excess nutrient content in the Soil Monitoring Directive.

Depending on weather (e.g., precipitation), topographic conditions (e.g., slope) and soil texture, N and P could be lost to the environment during unproductive periods, causing eutrophication of surface waters and ground water pollution. In particular, N is mainly lost via leaching in mineral form (nitrate). In all the investigated sites, nitrate was less than 12% total N (data not shown). Thus, it could be expected that the higher N observed in biodynamic treatments is stored in organic form as soil organic matter, thus linked to soil fertility.

Figure 8: Extractable P as affected by different management strategies and practices in InBestSoil agricultural sites (LH7: Atlantic, LL1: Mediterranean, LL2: Continental).

Several nutrients are taken up by plants as cations (e.g., potassium, calcium, magnesium, and more), which can be retained in the soil on negatively charged surfaces, such as clay minerals and soil organic matter. Cation exchange capacity represents the amount of positive charge (cations) that can be exchanged per mass of soil content, i.e. the amount of nutrients that a soil can retain and that can be taken up by plants. Thus, CEC is an indicator of soil fertility. In line with the other parameters, CEC was higher in the biodynamic management in LH7 compared to

the conventional, but it did not vary significantly among treatments in the other sites.

Figure 9: Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) as affected by different management strategies and practices in InBestSoil agricultural sites (LH7: Atlantic, LL1: Mediterranean, LL2: Continental).

7.3 Microbial biomass for soil biodiversity

Within the Soil Monitoring Directive soil biodiversity is defined as “the variation in soil life, from genes to communities of organisms, and the ecological complexes of which they are part, that is complexes ranging from soil micro-habitats to landscapes”. The complexity of soil biodiversity makes it difficult to identify indicators able to capture changes in response to management, although great progress in scientific knowledge has been made in recent years. Leveraging insights from several projects and studies, EJP Soil Deliverable 6.5 “Guidelines for accounting and mapping agricultural soil carbon, fertility and degradation changes at different scales” proposes a tiered approach for monitoring soil biodiversity, including both functional and structural bioindicators. Tier I group indicators are recommended in all cases, while more specific indicators could be measured depending on the context. Assessing ecosystem services related to soil

biodiversity is the specific focus of other projects funded by the Soil Mission (i.e., BIOserviceES and SOB4ES). Within this work, we report an indicator of total living microbial biomass (expressed as total phospholipid fatty acids, PLFAs), being aware of the limited information that can be derived from it. Although other indicators of soil biodiversity would provide a more robust assessment (e.g., DNA based), their measurement is still costly and difficult, and the results are less intuitive for non-experts. Except for LL1 Benatzu, total PLFAs tended to be higher in treatments with higher input of organic matter and reduced soil disturbance, i.e. biodynamic, organic and reduced or no tillage, although the increase was significant only in LH7 (Fig. 10).

Figure 10: Total PLFAs as affected by different management strategies and practices in InBestSoil agricultural sites (LH7: Atlantic, LL1: Mediterranean, LL2: Continental).

7.4 Overall effect of carbon farming practices on soil health aspects

The overall effect on soil health of carbon farming practices tested in InBestSoil LH7, LL1 and LL2 was either positive or neutral (Table 8). The practices implemented in the biodynamic regenerative management of LH7 generated a positive effect on soil structural quality (O/T SOC), nutrients availability (total N and

CEC) as well as microbial biomass (total PLFAs), compared to the conventional control. In LL1, reduced tillage and sod seeding had no effect on soil health indicators compared to conventional tillage in the Benatzu site, while soil structural quality and microbial biomass were improved in Ussana. In LL2, soil structural quality was improved by the biodynamic management to a larger extent than by biorganic and conventional with organic fertilization, while all three had a similar effect on microbial biomass. It should be noted that more than one carbon farming practice was implemented in LH7 and LL2, where different management systems were tested, while tillage intensity was the only factor considered in LL1.

Table 8: Summary of the impact of carbon farming practices on structural, chemical and biological aspects of soil health. Green indicates positive, light green slightly positive and yellow neutral effects.

Site	Management	Structural quality	Nutrients availability	Microbial biomass
LH7	Biodyn+reg	Green	Green	Green
LL1_B	Red till	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
	Sod seeding	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
LL1_U	Red till	Light green	Yellow	Light green
	Sod seeding	Light green	Yellow	Light green
LL2	Biodyn	Green	Yellow	Light green
	Biorg	Light green	Yellow	Light green
	Conv org+min fert	Light green	Yellow	Light green

8. Discussion and recommendations for policy updates

8.1 Limitations and critical issues

The aim of InBestSoil Task 6.2 was to investigate how soil health indicators could be included within carbon farming certification methodologies, proposing an approach that ensures accountability for multiple soil-related benefits. As methodologies for quantifying net carbon removals and soil emissions reductions are already being developed by the European Commission, in consultation with experts and stakeholders, those aspects were not extensively addressed in this report. Although SOC content and stock, as well as soil emissions were measured in InBestSoil case studies, data were not used to quantify Net carbon benefits since final methodologies are not yet available. Further, our data lack the temporal dimension required for assessing SOC-related benefits. However, it's important to underline that even if the carbon farming practices implemented in InBestSoil agricultural sites were shown to improve soil health, this is only considered as a co-benefit from a CRCF Regulation point of view. Thus, in this context, the certification of carbon removal or soil emission reduction unit(s) is a prerequisite.

Although voluntary co-benefits should generate a market premium for the certified units, the current debate at EU level suggests that they will not be quantified. This means that co-benefits will not have a numerical value, but will only be expressed as “positive impact”. As emerged during the workshop with InBestSoil case studies, establishing context-specific reference values for soil health indicators would enable a more robust assessment of the impact of carbon farming activities. In this regard, soil nutrient availability is a critical aspect. As discussed in section 7.2, higher N and P availability indicates both soil fertility and potential losses, depending on soil management and environmental conditions. According to the EU Soil Observatory, an extractable P content $> 50 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ soil indicates an excess, while values $< 20 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ soil represent P deficiency (Panagos et al., 2024). As shown in Figure 8, LH7 and LL2 exceed the higher threshold and could be considered at risk of P loss. Further, in Deliverable 6.5 EJP Soil highlights that “using a weak extraction method like Olsen P will say very little about the total P storage in the soil, which is important information for particulate P, lost through surface runoff or macro pore flow”. However, since soil cover is a key element to prevent soil nutrients losses, N and P content should be evaluated in connection to agricultural management.

8.2 Policy recommendations

To strengthen the Carbon Farming Certification Framework and ensure coherence with other relevant EU policies, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Embed soil health indicators in certification methodologies

- o Incorporate scientifically robust and cost-effective indicators, such as the Observed/Typical SOC (O/T SOC) index, into voluntary co-benefit certification.
- o Promote a multi-indicator approach combining physical, chemical, and biological metrics to capture the multifunctionality of soils.
- o Encourage the use of indicators that are intuitive for farmers and policymakers to facilitate adoption and compliance.
- o Assess cost-benefits for operators that adopt different certification methodologies during the pilot phase of the CRCF.

2. Align Carbon Farming Certification with the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive

- o Ensure alignment with soil descriptors of the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive.
- o Use data collected within soil units (defined by the Directive) as a baseline for evaluating improvements in soil health.

3. Develop context-specific reference values for key indicators

- o Establish regional benchmarks for soil health indicators to enable meaningful comparisons and robust assessment of co-benefits.
- o Integrate pedo-climatic zoning approaches (as in the O/T SOC index) to account for variability in soil properties and climate across Europe.

4. Promote synergies with CAP and Nature Restoration Regulation

- o Align voluntary co-benefit certification with CAP eco-schemes and agri-environment-climate measures to maximize incentives for farmers.

- o Ensure that mandatory co-benefits under the CRCF Regulation are consistent with restoration targets set by the Nature Restoration Regulation.

5. Address nutrient management in policy design

- o Integrate safeguards to prevent nutrient losses when promoting practices that increase soil fertility.
- o Link nitrogen and phosphorus indicators to management practices and environmental conditions to avoid trade-offs between soil health and water quality.

6. Support Capacity Building and Knowledge Sharing

- o Foster collaboration between Member States, research projects, and stakeholders to harmonize methodologies and share best practices.
- o Provide training and advisory services to farmers on soil health monitoring and interpretation of indicators.

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Annex I – Sensitive indicators to discriminate between different management in InBestSoil LHs and LLs, and associated soil ecosystem services.

Category	Soil ecosystem service	Most sensitive indicators								
		LH1 (Med. forest)	LH2 (Med. industrial)	LH3 (Atl. industrial)	LH4 (Cont. urban)	LH5 (Bor. urban)	LH6 (Bor. forest)	LH7 (Atl. agricultural)	LL1 (Med. agricultural)	LL2 (Cont. agricultural)
Provisioning	Provision of food	na	na	na	na	na	na	(not available)	Crop yield	Crop yield
	Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	NDVI	Vegetation cover	Forest cover; Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	na	na	Timber production	na	na	na
	Provision of water	Water content at field capacity				Water content at field capacity			Water content at field capacity	Water content at field capacity
Regulating	Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon; Albedo and land surface temperature	Total soil organic carbon; Particulate soil organic carbon; Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Total soil organic carbon; Particulate soil organic carbon; Carbon stock; Soil moisture; Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Total soil organic carbon; Potential soil CO2 emissions; Potential soil N2O emissions; Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Total soil organic carbon; Carbon stock; Potential soil CH4 emissions; Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Total soil organic carbon; Particulate soil organic carbon; Carbon stock; Soil moisture; Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Total soil organic carbon; particulate soil organic carbon; Net Primary Productivity	Particulate soil organic carbon; potential soil CO2 emissions; Net Primary Productivity	Carbon stock; Potential soil CO2 emissions; Potential soil CH4 emissions
	Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Total mercury; pH	Bioavailable cadmium; Bioavailable lead	Total lead; Total nickel; Total chromium	Total chromium; Total nickel; Total copper	Total copper; Total vanadium; Bioavailable vanadium;	na	na	na	na

						Bioavailable antimony; pH				
	Nutrient cycling	Available phosphorus; exchangeable magnesium	Tot nitrogen; Exchangeable potassium	Bioavailable boron; Exchangeable ammonium; Available phosphorus; Cation exchange capacity; Exchangeable calcium	Exchangeable calcium; Exchangeable potassium; Total nitrogen; Bioavailable zinc; pH	Exchangeable calcium; Exchangeable magnesium; Total nitrogen; Bioavailable boron; Bioavailable phosphorus; Cation exchange capacity	pH; Available phosphorus; Cation exchange capacity	Tot nitrogen; nitrates; bioavailable zinc; exchangeable magnesium; exchangeable potassium	Tot nitrogen; exchangeable ammonium; exchangeable magnesium; exchangeable potassium; cation exchange capacity	Tot nitrogen; Nitrates; Cation exchange capacity; Exchangeable calcium; pH; Bioavailable boron
	Flood regulation and water storage	Bulk density; water content at field capacity	Mean weight diameter of soil aggregates	Drought Stress Index (DSI)	Drought Stress Index (DSI); Bulk density; Soil porosity	Coarse fragments; Water content at field capacity	Drought Stress Index (DSI); Bulk density	Drought Stress Index (DSI); clay content; bulk density	Drought Stress Index (DSI); water content at field capacity; mean weight diameter of soil aggregates	Bulk density; Water content at field capacity; Mean weight diameter of soil aggregates
	Erosion control	Vegetation cover	Vegetation cover	Vegetation cover; Bare soil index (BSO)	Vegetation cover; Bare soil index (BSO)	Bare soil index (BSO)	Vegetation cover; Bare soil index (BSO)	Vegetation cover; bare soil index (BSO)	Vegetation cover; bare soil index (BSO)	Vegetation cover
Supporting	Biodiversity	Total PLFAs; Fungal Shannon Index; Fungal Chao1 Index	Total PLFAs; Zygomycota abundance; Fungal Chao1 Index; Prokaryotic Chao1 Index;	Total PLFAs; Bacterial biomass; Fungal biomass	Total PLFAs; Bacterial biomass; Zygomycota biomass; Actinomicota biomass;	Total PLFAs; Zygomycota biomass; Actinomicota biomass; Fungal Chao1 Index	Total PLFAs; Zygomycota abundance; Prokaryotic Shannon Index;	Firmiculites abundance; bacterial abundance; Fungal Chao1 Index	Total PLFAs; actinomicota biomass; bacterial abundance; Prokaryotic Simpson Index	Total PLFAs; Actinomicota biomass; Fungal Chao1 Index; Number of fungal amplicon

			Protists Chao1 Index		Prokaryotic Shannon Index; Fungal Chao1 Index		Prokaryotic Chao1 Index			sequence variants (ASV)
	Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Soil sealing	Plant density	Soil sealing	Presence of natural green elements (PGE)	Presence of natural green elements (PGE)	Presence of natural green elements (PGE)	Presence of natural green elements (PGE)	Soil sealing	Presence of natural green elements (PGE)

Annex II – Outcomes of the workshop with InBestSoil case studies on the interpretation of sensitive soil health indicators

LL1

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
NO	The analysis of 20 years of data showed no statistically significant differences among the 3 treatments. It depends also by year and weather...

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
NO	We expected significant higher POC levels under conservation treatments

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
YES	

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
NO	We expected higher soil aggregates in sod seeding (also with RT) due to reduced soil disturbance

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
NO	In our experience, there are no differences between conservation treatments (RT vs SS), nor between CT vs conservation managements. But it depends on years... Sometimes higher VEGCO values may be do to weeds...

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
NO	We expected higher bacterial abundance in RT and SS treatments

LL2

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	Differences are due to crops

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	Differences are due to soils and production systems

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	Differences are due to soil types and weathering status

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	Differences are due to soil types and production systems

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
More or less	Differences are due to production systems

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
No	The intensive conventional farms shows higher PLFA counts, while the biodynamic farms is clearly lower. I need more information on the method and a comparison with the experimental farms.

LH1

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
No	<p>With rotational grazing, we expect to increase forage availability. Long-term abandonment leads to bare soil.</p> <p>But not all NDVI is forage, that is the problem! so how to make a measurement for forage availability I do not know.</p>
<p>It's possible that the control was not adequate and we should have looked for a plot under conventional grazing. Likewise, perhaps the implementation of rotational grazing in LH1 was not yet advanced.</p>	
No	<p>In other studies with conventional management, we have obtained significant improvements in phosphorus under rotational grazing.</p>
No	<p>With rotational grazing, we expect to increase forage availability. Long-term abandonment leads to bare soil.</p>
I dont know	<p>If we had chosen a control under conventional or continuous grazing, we would expect higher organic carbon values under rotational grazing.</p>
Yes	<p>Livestock can compact the soil more, but if we had chosen a control under continuous grazing, we would expect higher bulk density in the control under rotational grazing.</p>
I dont know	<p>If we had chosen a control under conventional or continuous grazing, we would expect higher total P/LAs under rotational grazing.</p> <p>In other studies, we have found higher P/LAs under rotational grazing compared to conventional grazing, although the differences were not significant.</p>

LH2

<p>ND Vegetation Index *</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p> <p>NO</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p> <p>We expected better status of vegetation in reclaimed area</p>
<p>Exch. potassium (mg/kg) *</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p> <p>yes</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p> <p>Increased soil fertility owing to reclamation</p>
<p>Vegetation cover (%) *</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p> <p>yes</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p> <p>Reclamation led to increased colonization by vegetation</p>
<p>Particulate organic C (g/kg) *</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p> <p>yes</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p> <p>Reclamation led to increased organic matter in soil and so higher carbon sequestration</p>
<p>MWD of soil aggregates</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p> <p>yes</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p> <p>Reclamation led to improved soil structure and so infiltration and root development, and reduced erosion risk</p>
<p>Total PLFAs (nmol/g) *</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p> <p>yes</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p> <p>Reclamation led to increased microbial biomass and diversity</p>

LH3

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	Reclaimed area offered better conditions for soil

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Probably	Potential fertilization

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	Reclaimed area has an afforestation

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	Reclaimed area improved C content

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	More impact on the non-reclaimed area

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes	Reclaimed area has more biodiversity due to improvement in soil conditions (less contaminants and better conditions)

LH4

	<p>Total organic carbon (g/kg) DMOC</p> <p>0 = Cropland, 1 = Apple orchard, 2 = Grassland, 3 = Forest, 4 = Secondary forest</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p>
		<p>yes</p>	<p>that intensity of practices are strongly related to carbon accumulation.</p>
	<p>Drought Stress Index DMol</p> <p>0 = Cropland, 1 = Apple orchard, 2 = Grassland, 3 = Forest, 4 = Secondary forest</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p>
		<p>yes</p>	<p>cropland are most sensitive to water - drought fluctuations under direct impact of vegetation absence.</p>
	<p>Vegetation cover (%) DMol</p> <p>0 = Cropland, 1 = Apple orchard, 2 = Grassland, 3 = Forest, 4 = Secondary forest</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p>
		<p>yes</p>	<p>It tell us that tillage tremendously control this property. All other land uses have permanent cover and this graphics is expected.</p>
	<p>Exch. potassium (mg/kg) DM</p> <p>0 = Cropland, 1 = Apple orchard, 2 = Grassland, 3 = Forest, 4 = Secondary forest</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p>
		<p>No.</p>	<p>it tell us that perennial croplands have significantly higher dosages of nutrient addition. However, high potassium level in grasslands are not expected, especially in relation to the level in croplands.</p>
	<p>Bulk density (g/cm3) DM</p> <p>0 = Cropland, 1 = Apple orchard, 2 = Grassland, 3 = Forest, 4 = Secondary forest</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p>
		<p>yes</p>	<p>it tell us that annual plowing and traffic with machines compact the soil over the limit. Land uses without intensive management recorded loose topsoil.</p>
	<p>Total PLFAs (nmol/g) DMol</p> <p>0 = Cropland, 1 = Apple orchard, 2 = Grassland, 3 = Forest, 4 = Secondary forest</p>	<p>Was it as expected? (Yes/no)</p>	<p>What do they tell us? Comment</p>
		<p>yes</p>	<p>The observed PLFA gradient (forest > grassland > secondary forest > orchard > cropland) was expected and reflects a classic land use intensity gradient. Biological activity is higher in natural or semi-natural systems (forest, grasslands) indicating more active and diverse soil microbial communities. In opposite, it is lower in intensively managed systems (orchards, croplands), likely due to disturbance, lower organic input, and possibly chemical use.</p>

LH5: no answers provided

LH6: no answers provided

LH7

It is very hard to give any interpretation without an idea of what a desirable amount would be for this (or any) indicator. The soil tests farmers use usually give an indication of a desirable range for each indicator.

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Yes, our fertilisation is based largely on organic amendments and more resting crops. Seems a plausible outcome	We are doing well..?

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
We did not really think about it	Our plants experience less stress in drought?

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Depends	Is this a point in time or average over the year? In the second case we would have expected it because of cover crops. At time of sampling the cover was actually quite similar.

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Na	Difficult to interpret without knowing what is a desirable level of exc. potassium for optimal plant growth.

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
Not necessarily	Less compacted soil. Could be however a difference inherent to the soil itself as it is two different plots.

Was it as expected? (Yes/no)	What do they tell us? Comment
	We usually assume more life is better, so with that perspective it would mean we are doing something well, but actually we don't know. So I would not know what this number tells us.